

Geometric force operator on the imaginary geomenergy of G-dynamics

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Abstract

As a result of the G-dynamics and its corresponding imaginary geomenergy, we present some basic concepts such as geometric force and the geometric force operator based on imaginary geomenergy, the geometric potential, the potenergy and motor operator, as an application, we consider its use on the quantum harmonic oscillator.

Contents

1	The QCPB theory and quantum geometric bracket	1
1.1	Quantum covariant Hamiltonian system and the G-dynamics	2
2	The QCPB theory for quantum harmonic oscillator	4
3	Geometric force operator	5
3.1	Case one $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$	6
3.2	Geometric potential, the potenergy and motor operator	7
3.3	Geometric force and geometric force operator	8

1 The QCPB theory and quantum geometric bracket

In this section, we begin with some basic concepts of quantum covariant Poisson bracket and quantum geometric bracket. In quantum mechanics, quantum Poisson brackets $\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB}$ is the commutator of two operators \hat{f}, \hat{g} defined as $\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} = \hat{f}\hat{g} - \hat{g}\hat{f}$.

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Definition 1 (QCPB¹). *The QCPB is generally defined as*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

in terms of quantum operator \hat{f} , \hat{g} , where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = -G(s, \hat{g}, \hat{f})$ is called quantum geometric bracket.

It is zero if and only if \hat{f} and \hat{g} covariant commute, i.e. $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = 0$. It's clear to see that the QCPB as a generalization of the classical representation of the QPB theory allows a geometric bracket formula to exist on the manifold. As a result, it provides a new tool for us better understanding the quantum mechanics deeply.

Definition 2 (quantum geometric bracket). *The quantum geometric bracket is*

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

where s represents the globally condition of space.

As a consequence of the precise formulation of the quantum geometric bracket, the QCPB is completely written as

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

Obviously, the quantum geometric bracket as a correction term has remedied the defect of the classical QPB theory. In particular, the environment has joined the quantum process for the evolution of the observables. [see [1] for more details]

1.1 Quantum covariant Hamiltonian system and the G-dynamics

In this section, we will briefly review the entire theoretical framework of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system defined by the quantum covariant Poisson bracket.

Definition 3 (QCHS). *The QCHS defined by QCPB in terms of quantum operator \hat{f} , \hat{H} is generally given by*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$$

where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$ is quantum geobacket .

By using the quantum covariant Hamiltonian system, it directly leads to the emergence of the covariant dynamics including the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics. More precisely, the time covariant evolution of any observable \hat{f} in the covariant dynamics is given by both the generalized Heisenberg equation of motion and G-dynamics.

¹G. Wang. GSPB theory for GCHS and QCPB theory for QCHS. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3815068

Theorem 1 (The covariant dynamics). *The covariant dynamics, the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics can be formally formulated as*

The covariant dynamics: $\frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]$

The generalized Heisenberg equation: $\frac{d\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \hat{H} [s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$

G-dynamics: $\hat{w} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$.

respectively, where $\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} + \hat{w}$ is covariant time operator, and \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian and $[\cdot, \cdot]$ denotes the GGC of two operators.

Based on the G-dynamics, the imaginary geomenergy can be completely defined, we can better give a presentation for the covariant dynamics, ect.

Definition 4. *The imaginary geomenergy is defined by*

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$$

where \hat{w} is the G-dynamics.

As mentioned above, the imaginary geomenergy as an energy operator induced by the G-dynamics leads to the energy eigenvalues equation with the energy eigenvalues.

As a result, thusly, then a dynamical variable \hat{f} with the imaginary geomenergy defined above, then covariant dynamics is rewritten in the form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt}\hat{f} = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} + \hat{f}E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})$$

Obviously, if the covariant equilibrium equation $[\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = 0$ holds, then it yields $\frac{d}{dt}\hat{f} = -\hat{f}\hat{w}$, accordingly, \hat{f} is said to be a quantum covariant conserved quantity.

Since the G-dynamics as an independent new dynamics is discovered to picture the quantum mechanics, we have studied its precise properties. By using the imaginary geomenergy,

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} \tag{1}$$

as a energy operator for the state of the space. the G-dynamics can be rewritten as

$$\hat{w} = -\sqrt{-1}E^{(\text{Im})}/\hbar = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}$$

in general. Clearly, the G-dynamics mainly pictures the dynamical state created by the space itself, namely, the structure function s induces the G-dynamics for the dynamical properties of the space. Obviously, the G-dynamics represents the properties of the spatial manifolds. Furthermore, the (1) leads to the geometric wave equation given by

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}\psi = E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})\psi = [s, \hat{H}]_{QPB}\psi \tag{2}$$

for a given wave function ψ . [see [1, 3] for more details]

2 The QCPB theory for quantum harmonic oscillator

In this section, we simply review some basic results given by the paper [1,2] in QCPB. The time evolution of those operators depends on the Hamiltonian of the system. Considering the one-dimensional quantum harmonic oscillator,

$$\hat{H}^{(cl)} = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)2}}{2m} + \frac{m\omega^2 x^2}{2} \quad (3)$$

As a certain case, we will now start by briefly reviewing the quantum mechanics of a one-dimensional quantum harmonic oscillator (3). With the Hamiltonian given by (3), let's use the QCPB to recalculate the covariant evolution of the position and momentum operators. More specifically, the covariant dynamics in terms of the position reads

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt}x(t) = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \left[\hat{H}^{(cl)}, x(t) \right] = \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}(t)}{m} + x(t) \hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

By direct computation, the G-dynamics is given by

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)2} s + 2\hat{p}^{(cl)} s \hat{p}^{(cl)}}{2m} \quad (4)$$

And the generalized Heisenberg equation with respect to x follows

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}x(t) &= \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \left[\hat{H}^{(cl)}, x(t) \right]_{QPB} + \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \hat{H}^{(cl)} [s, x(t)]_{QPB} \\ &= \frac{\hat{p}^{(cl)}(t)}{m} \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, the covariant dynamics for the classical momentum operator is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt}\hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) &= \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \left[\hat{H}^{(cl)}, \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \right] \\ &= -m\omega^2 x - \hat{H}^{(cl)} u + \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \hat{w}^{(cl)} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)}/b_c = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx}u \quad (5)$$

has been used and $ds/dx = u$ is denoted and $b_c = -\frac{\sqrt{-1}\hbar}{2m}$. Accordingly, the generalized Heisenberg equation in terms of the $\hat{p}^{(cl)}$ appears

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}\hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) &= \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \left[\hat{H}^{(cl)}, \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t) \right]_{QPB} + \frac{\sqrt{-1}}{\hbar} \hat{H}^{(cl)} [s, \hat{p}^{(cl)}(t)]_{QPB} \\ &= -m\omega^2 x - \hat{H}^{(cl)} u \end{aligned}$$

As we can see, clearly, the variables $u, \hat{w}^{(cl)}$ are fundamental building blocks for the foundation of the quantum mechanics.

According to (2), the geometric wave equation in terms of G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ (5) is written in a precise form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(2u \frac{d\psi}{dx} + \psi \frac{du}{dx} \right) \quad (6)$$

its solution for a geometric wave function $\psi = C_0\Gamma(u, w^{(q)})$ can be directly computed and given by

$$\Gamma(u, w^{(q)}) = u^{-1/2} \exp \left(\sqrt{-1}a_c^{-1} \int \frac{w^{(q)}}{u} dx \right) \quad (7)$$

for the eigenvalues $w^{(q)}$ of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, namely, $\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = w^{(q)}\psi$, where $a_c = \hbar/m$. As we can easily checked, the variables $u, w^{(q)}$ are two basic parameters for the new properties of the quantum mechanics, they form the fundamental data to reform the spatial dynamics. In particular, $u, w^{(q)}$ form the geometric wave-particle duality.

Actually, let's take the geometric wave equation (6) to another familiar form like

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}\psi = \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})\psi = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(2u \frac{d\psi}{dx} + \psi \frac{du}{dx} \right) \quad (8)$$

where we denote $E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \hat{H}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)})$. Notice that it's the same as the Schrödinger equation in form, but its formulation is more easier than Schrödinger equation.

3 Geometric force operator

In this section, we introduce the geometric force operator based on the G-dynamics, more precisely, the geometric force operator is deduced by the space derivative of the imaginary geomenergy.

Based on the imaginary geomenergy, we can naturally deduce the geometorce operator

$$\hat{F}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \partial_j E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_j\hat{w} = \partial_j \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB}$$

as a geometric force operator which can be considered in quantum mechanics. More formally, its formulation can be directly obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{F}^{(\text{Im})}\phi &= \partial_j \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} \phi = \partial_j \left(s\hat{H}\phi - \hat{H}(s\phi) \right) \\ &= \partial_j \left(s\hat{H}\phi \right) - \partial_j \hat{H}(s\phi) \\ &= \partial_j s\hat{H}\phi + s\partial_j \hat{H}\phi - \partial_j \hat{H}(s\phi) \\ &= A_j \hat{H}\phi + s\partial_j \hat{H}\phi - \partial_j \hat{H}(s\phi) \\ &= F^{(\text{Im})}\phi \end{aligned}$$

where $A_j = \partial_j s$ is the structural derivative, $F^{(\text{Im})}$ is the eigenvalue in terms of a given wave function ϕ , and thusly, then it derives the precise formula of the geometorce operator

$$\hat{F}^{(\text{Im})} = \partial_j \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} = A_j \hat{H} + s\partial_j \hat{H} - \partial_j \hat{H} s$$

3.1 Case one $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$

In this section, we mainly consider the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ as a precise case, by doing this, we can get its corresponding geometorce operator in a certain formula. Actually, the G-dynamics (4) is derived by using the formulation

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QPB}$$

As a consequence, the imaginary geomenergy in terms of the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ follows

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)} = \left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QPB}$$

As a certain model, we mainly focus on the G-dynamics (5) $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$, its corresponding geometorce operator is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{F}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) &= \partial_j E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) = \partial_j \left[s, \hat{H}^{(cl)} \right]_{QPB} \\ &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar\partial_j\hat{w}^{(cl)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In one-dimensional form, $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ is certainly expressed as

$$\hat{w}^{(cl)} = b_c \left(2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx} \right)$$

Plugging $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$ in one-dimensional into (9), then it yields geometorce operator with respect to the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{F}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} = \sqrt{-1}\hbar b_c \frac{d}{dx} \left(2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{du}{dx} \right) \\ &= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(2u \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + 3 \frac{du}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d^2u}{dx^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where the derivation is taken

$$\frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} \phi = 2b_c u \frac{d^2\phi}{dx^2} + 3b_c \frac{du}{dx} \frac{d\phi}{dx} + b_c \phi \frac{d^2u}{dx^2}$$

Accordingly, it derives

$$\frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} = 2b_c u \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + 3b_c \frac{du}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + b_c \frac{d^2u}{dx^2}$$

The geometorce operator as a mechanical operator has its eigenvalue equation given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{F}^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}^{(cl)}) \psi &= \sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} \psi \\ &= \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(2u \frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + 3 \frac{du}{dx} \frac{d\psi}{dx} + \psi \frac{d^2u}{dx^2} \right) \\ &= F^{(\text{Im})} \psi \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Geometric potential, the potenergy and motor operator

In this section, we wish to further discuss the coordinates derivative of the geometric potential, the potenergy and motor operator, respectively. [see [4] for more details]

Quantum potential as part of the Schrödinger equation, the Schrödinger equation

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = \widehat{H}^{(cl)}\psi = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V\right)\psi \quad (10)$$

is rewritten using the polar form for the wave function $\psi = A^{(b)}\exp(\sqrt{-1}S/\hbar)$ with real-valued functions $A^{(b)}$ and S , where $A^{(b)}$ is the amplitude (absolute value) of the wave function ψ , and S/\hbar its phase. The quantum potential is naturally obtained

$$Q^{(cl)} = a_1 \frac{\nabla^2 A^{(b)}}{A^{(b)}}.$$

where $a_1 = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}$ is used.

Consider one dimensional case, then the geometric potential can be expressed as

$$Q^{(g)} = a_1 \left(2u \frac{d \ln A^{(b)}}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx}u\right) + a_1 u^2$$

By plugging the G-dynamics $\hat{w}^{(cl)}/b_c = 2u \frac{d}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx}u$ into above one dimensional case, and then the geometric potential rewrites

$$Q^{(g)} = E^{(wg)} + a_1 u^2 = a_1 u^2 - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}A^{(b)}/A^{(b)}$$

where the potenergy $E^{(wg)}$ is

$$E^{(wg)} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}A^{(b)}/A^{(b)}$$

and quantum potential is $Q^{(cl)} = \frac{a_1}{A^{(b)}} \frac{d^2 A^{(b)}}{dx^2}$. Accordingly, the geometric quantum potential is totally rewritten in a form

$$Q^{(s)} = \widehat{E}^{(w)}A^{(b)}/A^{(b)} + a_1 u^2$$

where motor operator in one-dimensional case is

$$\widehat{E}^{(w)} = a_1 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w}^{(cl)}$$

Note that the representation of the potenergy $E^{(wg)}$ is pretty similar to the formulation of the quantum potential $Q^{(cl)}$, based on this similarity for both formula, it directly leads to the combination of the motor operator. Meanwhile, it potentially reveals the parallel function between the potenergy $E^{(wg)}$ as a new kind of the quantum energy and quantum potential $Q^{(cl)}$. That's why we have generalized the quantum potential to be more general form called the geometric quantum potential which can be formulated as

$$Q^{(s)} = Q^{(cl)} + Q^{(g)}$$

Clearly, the geometric potential $Q^{(g)}$ as a correction term for quantum potential $Q^{(cl)}$ is definitely needed, especially, the existence of the potenergy $E^{(wg)}$ rationally appears.

More importantly, we notice that the geometric wave equation (8) independently in form is very similar to the Schrödinger equation (10), they make a whole system for describing the quantum mechanics completely, at the same time, the solution of geometric wave equation (8) can be easily deduced, shown by the geometric wave function (7).

3.3 Geometric force and geometric force operator

This section will argue the geometric force and geometric force operator separately according to the geometric potential and the potenergy, motor operator introduced earlier.

The geometric force induced by the geometric potential in terms of the space x is according derived

$$\begin{aligned} F^{(g)} &= \frac{dQ^{(g)}}{dx} = 2a_1u \frac{du}{dx} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)} \\ &= a_1 \left(2 \frac{d \ln A^{(b)}}{dx} \frac{du}{dx} + 2u \frac{d^2 \ln A^{(b)}}{dx^2} + \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \right) + 2a_1u \frac{du}{dx} \\ &= F^{(wg)} + 2a_1u \frac{du}{dx} \end{aligned}$$

where the focergy is given by

$$\begin{aligned} F^{(wg)} &= \frac{d}{dx} E^{(wg)} = -\sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} A^{(b)} / A^{(b)} \\ &= a_1 \left(2 \frac{d \ln A^{(b)}}{dx} \frac{du}{dx} + 2u \frac{d^2 \ln A^{(b)}}{dx^2} + \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

induced by the coordinate derivative of the potenergy.

Similarly, motor operator also leads to another geometric force operator given a name motorce operator

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{F}^{(w)} &= \frac{d}{dx} \hat{E}^{(w)} = a_1 \frac{d^3}{dx^3} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \hat{w}^{(cl)} \\ &= a_1 \frac{d^3}{dx^3} - \sqrt{-1}\hbar \left(2b_c u \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + 3b_c \frac{du}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + b_c \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \right) \\ &= a_1 \frac{d^3}{dx^3} - \hat{F}^{(Im)} (\hat{w}^{(cl)}) \end{aligned}$$

This has given the relation between the geometorce operator $\hat{F}^{(Im)} (\hat{w}^{(cl)})$ and motorce operator $\hat{F}^{(w)}$. Thusly, then its eigenvalue equation can be given

$$\hat{F}^{(w)} \varphi = a_1 \frac{d^3 \varphi}{dx^3} - \hat{F}^{(Im)} (\hat{w}^{(cl)}) \varphi = F^{(w)} \varphi$$

with respect to the wave function φ , where $F^{(w)}$ is called the motorce as an eigenvalue.

Above all, it surely provides a grand-new way to realize exactly how the quantum mechanics works in a certain way. A series of different geometric force and geometric force operator are derived to picture a complete dynamics of moving particles, it implies that a real quantum mechanics is more complicated than we think before. Such new perspectives give us new tool to understand the quantum mechanics and the general relativity.

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